

Numerical data of strong-gravity solutions with fundamental fields and its signatures

Version 1

Description

This is a plan to share numerical data generated in the project 2025.09507.CPCA, within the Call for Advanced Computing Projects (6th ed), supported by Fundação da Ciência e Tecnologia, Portugal. The data will include a representative selection of three types of solutions: 1-Einstein-Proca Stars Without Isometries, 2-Non-Circular Spacetimes in the Einstein-Klein-Gordon Model; 3-Spinning Non-Uniform Black Strings in 5D Gravity. The dataset also includes synthetic images of these solutions, generated by numerical ray-tracing. Due to its large volume, additional data can be shared upon request.

Funder

Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P. | FCT

Grant

Towards precision tests of ultralight dark matter with gravitational waves and imaging
(fct_____::2024.05617.CERN)

Researchers

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Organizations

Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia, Universidade de Aveiro, Department of Mathematics, Center for Research & Development in Mathematics and Applications, Gravitational Geometry and Dynamics Group

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Numerical data of strong-gravity solutions with fundamental fields and its signatures

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P. | FCT

Grants: Towards precision tests of ultralight dark matter with gravitational waves and imaging (fct_____:2024.05617.CERN)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

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Template: [FCT - Template in English](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 DATA INFORMATION

1.1 What existing data will be re-used?

1.1.1 Will you re-use existing data for this project?

No

1.2 What data will be created or produced?

1.2.1 Will new data be created in this project?

Yes

1.2.2 Describe the data you expect your research will generate.

a. numeric (solutions of spacetimes)

b. images (synthetic observational images)

1.2.3 Describe the data format you expect your research will generate.

a. .txt

b. .jpg

c. .png

1.3 What is the data volume?

1.3.1 How much data storage will your project require in total?

>1000 GB

2 DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

2.1 Documentation

2.1.1 Indicate what documentation will accompany the data.

A pdf document will accompany the data, explaining the content, notation, and organization of the files

2.2 Metadata

2.2.1 Is there metadata associated with the data?

No

3 STORAGE AND SECURITY OF DATA AND METADATA

3.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.1.1 Describe where the data and metadata will be stored during the project.

Institution networked research storage

3.1.3 Is there a policy in place for data backups during the project?

Yes

In addition to a data storage unit of the institution, we shall have data backup in a personal hard drive

3.1.4 Please describe the type of backup.

Offsite backup

3.1.5 Please describe the frequency of backup.

Unknown

3.2 Protection and security of sensitive data

3.2.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

Not applicable (no sensitive data)

4 PERSONAL DATA, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS AND OWNERSHIP

4.1 How will you handle issues regarding the processing of personal information and intellectual property rights and ownership?

4.1.1 Will you process and/or store personal data during your project?

No

4.1.3 How will ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data be managed?

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The PI and co-PI of the computational project will be responsible for the ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data

5 DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

5.1 Long-term data preservation

5.1.1 How will data be selected for long-term preservation?

All data resulting from the project will be preserved for at least 10 years

5.2 Data available for re-use

5.2.1 What data will be made available for re-use?

Other (please specify)

5.2.2 Please specify.

The total amount of data is too large (almost 1.6TB), so the plan is to share a curated selection of the data, of around 50GB. Further data can be shared upon request.

5.2.3 When will the data be available for re-use, and for how long will the data be available?

Data available as soon as article is published

To be given appropriate credit and context, the data will be shared upon completion of the corresponding published article.

5.2.4 In which repository will the data be archived and made available for re-use, and under which license?

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Zenodo

5.2.5 Please confirm if:

- The repository is registered in the re3data directory
- The repository is aggregated in OpenAIRE
- The repository is certified

5.2.6 Please indicate whether a persistent identifier will be pursued.

Yes

DOI

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

5.2.7 Under which license will the data be archived and made available for re-use?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

5.2.8 Describe your strategy for publishing the analysis software that will be generated in this project.

No special or specific software needed.

6 RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

6.1 Responsibilities and resources for data management

6.1.1 Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management?

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data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; and data sharing.

6.1.2 What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?

Data storage will be initially supported by the HPC storage(MareNostrum/Deucalion) during computation; long-term storage at University of Aveiro; Zenodo for curated readily sharable deposit, which is free until a 50GB user limit.

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